

A STUDY ON THE OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF TRADE UNION IN TANCEM, ARIYALUR DISTRICT

Dr. K. Maruthadurai

Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, Thanthai Hans Roever
College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Industrial Relations are the complex of human relationships which emerge in work situations. These situations bring people together for services which are bought and sold at a price. The maintenance of good human relationships is the main theme of industrial relations, because in its absence the whole organisational structure may fall down. The main aim is to study to find out and measure the operational performance of trade union. It is descriptive in nature; this study tries to address the importance, objective, obstacles and challenges involved in the maintenance of industrial relations in public cement companies. The researcher has used different variables in this study to find out workers problems solved by trade unions and suggest to management which must have a smooth relationship with the trade unions to reduce unnecessary conflict between them.

Introduction:

Industrial relations play a crucial role in establishing and maintaining industrial democracy. The establishment of good industrial relations depends on the constructive attitude on the part of both the management and the unions. The maintenance of good human relationships is the main theme of industrial relations, because in its absence the whole edifice of organisational structure may crumble. Industrial relation is an art of living together for the purpose of production, productive efficiency, human well-being and industrial progress. The existence of good human relations, organised labour movement, collective bargaining, fair dealing by management with the workers, joint consultation at all levels, etc. is necessary for the establishment and maintenance of harmonious industrial relations and for building up new attitudes and institutions.

Objective of the Study:

To find out and measure the operational performance of Trade Union.

Review of Literature:

Gomez-Mejia et al (2005) stated that, industrial organisations for their survival in competitive market condition have given emphasis on gaining support from employees, mutual trust and confidence building, importance on unions, improved career and salary tracks, retirement benefits, and retraining measures.

Pettinger.R. (1999) opined that, now trade union is adopting a cooperative attitude towards the management in contrast to the previous confrontationist attitude. At the core of this, it is a fundamental shift in the relationship between employers and trade unions, following the gradual realisation between employers and trade unions, following the gradual realisation that the interests of all are the best served through harmonious rather than adversarial industrial relations.

Statement of the Problem:

The industrial relation is the key to bring and achieve the desired target of any business. In this same context, to keep the sustainable growth and development of any cement company, it has to maintain the smooth industrial relation becomes inevitable. Since a decade a healthy competition is going on between cement companies, and this trend forcing all corners of the social researchers to turn their attention towards this issue of Industrial Relations. Due to these unlimited growths of cement companies, the maintenance of industrial harmony or relation is becoming a crucial role, and a challenging task. However the maintenance of industrial relations is concerned such as the working environment, salary and wage pattern, motivational methods, freedom, self role and etc., In public Ltd., cement companies there is an enough amount of freedom and autonomous to the working population is decided to focus his attention and to select this issue as a title for his research work.

Significance of the Study:

In today's fast changing industrial world, too many relevant issues have to be addressed and to draw suitable solutions within the stipulated timeframe. Among several issues of industrial world, to avoid industrial disputes and maintain smooth industrial relation is the most vital one. To maintain the industrial relation in any industry/company, several variables and attributes have to be identified and addressed. It is a challenging task in the today's environment, especially in manufacturing industries, because, the level of understanding, awareness, amount of flexibility and tolerance are not up to the standard among both employers and employees. This study is try to address the importance, objectives, obstacles and challenges involved in the maintenance of industrial relations in public and private Ltd., cement companies which are located at Tamil Nadu with special reference to Ariyalur District. In this background, the researcher has selected this issue as a title for his research work.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

Research design is acting like a lighthouse and it is passing the light and direction throughout the research voyage. The research design can be of different kinds and modes, it depends upon the nature of the problem, data and analyses. The research design which is concerned with this title is descriptive in nature. Because this study is trying to describe the characteristics of different existing variables of the selected problem.

Sampling Method:

The total employee strength of TANCEM is 376 and all employees were distributed with questionnaire. They have been provided enough time to fill – up the questionnaire. Finally, the researcher was only able to collect 365 duly filled questionnaires from the respondents and 11 questionnaires were unable to recollect from the employees. Hence the sample size of this study is 365.

Analytical Tools Used in This Study:

The following statistical tools have been used in this study to analyse the collected data:

- ✓ Percentage Analysis
- ✓ Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)
- ✓ Regression

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Percentage Distribution of Members of the trade union

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	303	83
No	62	17
Total	365	100

Trade unions are normally strong in public limited companies. They provide all the measure for the welfare of the co-employees. In Arasu cements, the trade union functions well. Among the employees surveyed for this study, 83 per cent of them are members in the trade union. Only 17 per cent are not members in trade union. All the trade union members opine that the participation of trade union is more in almost all the activities of the organisation.

Table 2: Percentage Distribution of attending trade union meetings regularly

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	301	82.5
No	64	17.5
Total	365	100

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the employees' opinion about regular participation in the meeting of trade union. It is noted that 82.5 per cent of the employees agree that they regularly attend trade union meetings, but only 17.5 per cent of the employees are not agreeing to this statement, which means that they do not regularly attend the trade union meetings.

Influence of Demographic variables on Level of Satisfaction on Trade Union Performance:

Education	Level of Satisfaction of Present Salary			F	p -value	Multiple Comparison
	N	Mean	SD			
Below ESLC	9	3.778	.972	4.461	<0.001	Graduation Vs. ESLC, SSLC, post graduation
ESLC	34	4.000	.492			
SSLC	109	3.606	.667			
HSc	74	3.541	.666			
Graduation	74	3.189	1.289			
Post graduation	35	3.771	.426			
Technical qualification	30	3.600	1.037			
Total	365	3.564	.867			
Age						
Below 41 years	47	3.636	.505	3.143	0.044	Above 50 years Vs. 41 – 50 years
41 to 50 years	151	3.375	.943			
Above 50 years	167	3.632	.842			
Total	365	3.564	.867			
Level of Employment						
Unskilled	49	3.531	.544	5.507	0.004	Highly Skilled Vs. Semi-skilled
Semi-skilled	194	3.443	.881			
Highly skilled	122	3.770	.916			
Total	365	3.564	.867			
Monthly Income						

Below Rs.15001	51	3.235	.586	5.438	0.005	Above Rs.16000, Rs.15001-Rs.16000 Vs. Below Rs.15001
Rs.15001 to Rs. 16000	117	3.709	.766			
Above Rs.16000	197	3.563	.960			
Total	365	3.564	.867			
Other Source of Income						
Rent	68	3.441	.870	2.024	0.110	NS
Agriculture	241	3.631	.759			
Private Business	27	3.593	1.309			
Others	29	3.276	1.131			
Total	365	3.564	.867			

In order to identify the influence, ANOVA has been performed and the results are shown in the above table. Among the five demographic variables, except other source of income, all the variables have significantly influence on the dependent variable and level of satisfaction on trade union performance. To know the mean difference among the influencing variables, Post hoc Bonferroni test was applied and the results are shown in the table.

Regarding education ($F = 4.461$; $p < 0.001$), employees who have finished graduation (mean = 3.189; SD = 1.289) significantly differ from the employees who have completed ESLC (mean = 4.000; SD = 0.492), SSLC (mean = 3.606; SD = 0.667) and post-graduation qualification (mean = 3.771; SD = 0.426), which means that the satisfaction level of graduated employees is significantly lower than that of the employees with ESLC, SSLC and post-graduate qualifications towards the operational performance of Trade Union.

In the case of age ($F = 3.143$; $p = 0.044$), employees who are in the age group of above 50 years (mean = 3.632; SD = 0.842) is significantly differ from the employees who are in the age group of 41 to 50 years (mean = 3.375; SD = 0.943). That is, aged employees are highly satisfied with the trade union performance compared to middle aged employees.

With regard to level of employment ($F = 5.507$; $p = 0.004$), highly skilled employees (mean = 3.770; SD = 0.916) significantly differ from semi-skilled employees (mean = 3.443; SD = 0.881) towards the level of satisfaction on trade union performance. That is, the satisfaction level of highly skilled employees towards trade union performance is higher than that of semi-skilled employees.

Considering monthly income ($F = 5.438$; $p = 0.005$), employees who earn more than Rs.16000 per month (mean = 3.563; SD = 0.960) and Rs.15001 to Rs.16000 (mean = 3.709; SD = 0.766) significantly differ from the employees who earn below Rs.15001 (mean = 3.235; SD = 0.586), which means that the highly paid and moderately paid employees are highly satisfied with the performance of trade union when compared to their counterpart.

Findings:

- ✓ In TANCEM cements, the trade union functions well. Among the employees surveyed for this study, 83 per cent of them are members in the trade union. Only 17 per cent are not members in trade union. All the trade union members opine that the participation of trade union is more in almost all the activities of the organisation.
- ✓ It is noted that 82.5 per cent of the employees agree that they regularly attend trade union meetings, but only 17.5 per cent of the employees are not agreeing to this statement, which means that they do not regularly attend the trade union meetings.

Conclusion:

The term "Industrial Relations" comprises of several attributes and it has come across many evolutions and revolutions, over the period. The analysis of this study revealed many outcomes regarding the status of industrial relations pertaining to TANCEM. The performance of trade unions is also looking satisfactory in TANCEM. In any company atmosphere and that too in public ltd., companies keeping cent per cent satisfaction over all wings are impossible. However the TANCEM management in concentrating and contributing due and equal importance on all variables of industrial relations and it is concluded that the status and level of industrial relations in TANCEM is in normal and acceptable level.

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